

THE USE OF AUDIOVISUAL MEDIA AS AN INTRODUCTION TO LOCAL CULTURE FOR FOREIGN STUDENTS PARTICIPATING IN INDONESIAN LEARNING

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Abstract

Learning a language is a step towards mastering the "language". The success of the "language" learning step is influenced by two important elements, namely teachers and students. Similarly, learning Indonesian for Foreign Languages (BIPA) requires students to master language and literature skills. Especially for BIPA Junior High School students. The learning process is "said to be successful if" the competencies taught by the teacher or teacher can be mastered well by students. There needs to be preparation done by the teacher before passing on these competencies to students. Especially for BIPA students, literature must be quite foreign to them even though only a few are familiar with literature in their respective countries. Therefore, BIPA educators must use various innovative learning tricks, one of which is by applying learning media according to the competencies that will be taught by BIPA students. Learning and getting to know Indonesian culture is a great way to teach using audio-visual media in the form of videos. Video media is a media that displays images, gestures, and sounds that will make the learning process for BIPA students more fun and easier, while introducing the cultural diversity of Indonesia to BIPA learners.

Keywords: Indonesian; BIPA; Audio-visual Media.

1. INTRODUCTION

Indonesian is one of the world's languages that have made significant progress. This fact can be proven from the many countries that have studied Indonesian which until now number up to more than forty-five countries in the world. This has made a significant increase, one of which is an increase in the number of higher education institutions and teaching institutions that provide course services for Indonesian for Foreign Speakers (BIPA).

Foreign learners who want to understand Indonesian usually learn about the formal variety commonly used in Indonesian. This happens because Indonesian teachers generally do not explain colloquial language (Sneddon, 1990). Sarumpaet says: This is exacerbated by a better condition for foreign students to make mistakes in correct and formal language than to use a variety of non-standard and incorrect language which is the reference of the teacher Indonesian.

The absence of non-formal variety teaching Indonesian has the potential to expose foreign speakers studying Indonesian linguistic shock when they attempt to converse informally with Indonesian-speaking communities.

BIPA is an acronym for Indonesian for Foreign Speakers. The meaning of Indonesian is the official language of Indonesia. This language has undergone many developments and then used as a means of communication by Indonesian Speakers themselves (BIPI) and by Foreign Speakers (BIPA) (Widiatmika, M., I Gede Mahendra Darmawiguna, 2019). To be able to communicate well, BIPA must undergo an intensive learning process.

Semarang State University (UNNES) through the Unit of the Education and Professional Development Institute (LP3) which has developed the BIPA Program.

Students studying the BIPA program are foreign students who has a different language and cultural background from Indonesia. The inequality between culture and language is also has consequences in the choice of Indonesian material taught to foreign students, because the acquisition of a second language, is strongly influenced by the original language of the student (Ellis, 2012). Kusmiatun also defines learners BIPA, is a person who does not speak Indonesian or even have never spoken Indonesian as a means of communication, although it does not rule out the possibility that he can already master foreign languages from other countries besides Indonesian. The ability to learn BIPA varies, ranging from beginner-level learners, intermediate levels to advanced learners. This is what distinguishes so that various kinds of BIPA material arise (Kusmiatun, 2016). Suyitno also continued that in BIPA materials there were authors, both Indonesian and foreign writers who contributed to the writing of the material. The aim is to make it easier for students to understand the Indonesian language in their learning, Although in reality there is a lot of variation in terms of approach, teaching techniques, teaching materials, and sequences that each author thinks that the book he compiled is a book that Most effective for Indonesian lessons for foreign students (Suyitno, 2007).

The importance of learning media delivered by Dale there are eleven levels based on the level of concreteness to the most abstract, namely direct understanding, experience through artificial objects, experience through drama, demonstration, field trips, television, film, radio, visual, visual and verbal symbols (Dale, 1954). Knowledge can be gained through direct experience and indirect experience. The more direct the object studied, the more concrete knowledge is obtained; The more indirect the knowledge is obtained, the more abstract the student's knowledge will be.

To be able to produce learners Indonesian who can understand the cultural context and linguistics, the author considers that Learning Language must be supported with materials and methods that appropriate. So far BIPA material the existing ones are still conventional and Still a little bit BIPA material that combines between materials audiovisual and Comprehensive local load. In the context of use multimedia and culture-based foreign language learning, BIPA learning is still far behind compared to English language learning. The use of multimedia is a matter of great urgency considering the advancement of information technology today. In addition, the use of multimedia will also make it easier for learners to learn various language experiences and Indonesian culture. Therefore, the author argues that BIPA learning needs to use a combination of multimedia touch and local cultural content. Previous studies have placed more emphasis on aspects (Barnard et al., 2002), (Richards & Rodgers, 2010), (Kumaravadivelu, 2006) while other studies apply (Fujisaki et al., 2004), (Friedman et al., 2011). Based on the description above, this study aims to complement previous studies and focus on the use of audiovisual media as an introduction to local culture for foreign students participating in Indonesian learning.

Based on the explanation that the author has described, this study was conducted to describe and explain that the use of audio-visual media is the right media as an introduction to local Indonesian culture for foreign students studying in Indonesia, commonly called BIPA Students.

The BIPA material that has been given is expected to be an alternative BIPA material that accommodates the needs of learners to know the applicable Indonesian language and culture.

2. METHODS

This research is a qualitative descriptive research using a case study strategy. The research method will be carried out using observational interview techniques. The form of data from this study is in the form of interviews, observations, and documents.

The source of data in this study was obtained from secondary BIPA students who had graduated and were able to identify various kinds of Indonesian culture as one of the the ability he has. Not only that, the author also uses literature studies as a source data on this study. Validity tests are performed using triangulation methods (H. Mudjia Rahardjo, 2010).

The form of data in the form of interviews, observations, and documents is compared with findings that have been studied before. Furthermore, the data analysis technique to be carried out refers to theory (Sugiyono, 2016) regarding interactive qualitative. Researchers conducted in-depth interviews with informants. Researchers engage interactively with informants so as to discover some new knowledge. Based on these new findings, researchers can present and conclude them.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Foreign students Indonesian come from various parts of the world, they also have language and culture from their own regions. In addition, they also have differences in language and culture which of course are very different from the diversity of languages and cultures that he will learn in Indonesia. It also has an effect on the use of Indonesian material that will be taught to foreign students studying Indonesian. The use of inappropriate material can affect the occurrence of difficulties and boredom from foreign learners in pursuing their studies (Suyitno, 2007). One of the goals of Indonesian learning students (BIPA) is that they want to run smoothly in talking Indonesian and being able to get to know Indonesian culture more closely.

Fluency in terms of Indonesian language is needed for BIPA students because they have considered various goals, namely first, taking programs about Indonesia at the university he comes from, second, they will conduct research in Indonesia, third, they will work in Indonesia, fourth, they will research Indonesian problems, and finally they will stay in Indonesia for a long time. A brief overview of the learning objectives of BIPA is implicated in the preparation of learning materials that are in accordance with these objectives. Thus, this research is closely related to the problem of meeting the needs of foreign student learners.

Middle-level BIPA students are required to be able to provide observations of events that they have experienced and be able to express ideas from what they have done in accordance with their expertise, both concretely and abstractly, quite smoothly without any obstacles that disturb speech partners. This is one of the achievement points contained in Permendikbud RI Number 27 of 2007. The results of this study show that intermediate BIPA learners have difficulty mastering and understanding Indonesian culture, including in interpreting a speech.

Based on the acquisition of learning outcomes that have been designed in BIPA teaching, the steps chosen are communicative steps, which emphasize that this is the nature of language and language learning. This is in accordance with the opinion (Barnard et al., 2002) which explains that the assumption of communicative steps regarding the nature of language is that language is a system in expressing meaning, as a tool for humans to communicate and interact, the structure of language reflects the function of its use and communicative function, and the main unit of language is not only grammatical but the function and meaning of communication.

Based on observations and interviews, it turns out that students who come to study in Indonesia one of them aims to get to know more about Indonesia. From this statement, problems were found such as

- (1) Low understanding of the use of words owned by students. Even though they have been in Indonesia for quite a long time, it does not rule out the possibility that foreign students also have difficulty digesting a sentence. Often their ignorance in expressing speech so they express it with sign language.
- (2) Lack of learning media as a learning guide for students in BIPA learning.
- (3) Students must also know the culture in Indonesia.

In language learning, it is also important that the media. Learning media can be classified into 3 (three) parts, namely

- (a) Judging from the nature of the media is divided into 3 (three), namely auditive media is media that can be heard only, visual media, this media can only be seen without containing sound elements, and audiovisual media, this type of media in addition to containing sound elements also contains image elements that can be seen
- (b) seen from its range ability, media can also be divided into media that have a wide and simultaneous coverage capacity such as radio and television, and media that have limited coverage power by space and time
- (c) Judging from the way and technique of use the media is divided into 2 (two) parts, namely projected media such as films, slides and so on that require special projection tools such as projector films, and non-projected media such as drawings, photographs, paintings, and so on (Sanjaya, 2010).

In general, media is the plural of *medium*, which means intermediary or introduction. The term of the media used in the field of teaching or education so that the term becomes a medium of education and learning.

However, media is not only in the form of tools or materials, but other things that allow students to obtain Knowledge. Gerlach and Ely state: *A medium, conceived is any person, material or event that establishes condition which enable the learner to acquire knowledge, skill, and attitude* (Evans, 1976).

According to Gerlach, media generally includes people, materials, equipment, or activities that create conditions that allow students to acquire knowledge, skills, and attitudes.

This understanding means that the media is not only an intermediary tool such as television, radio, printed materials, but includes people or humans as a source of learning or also in the form of activities such as discussions, seminars, tourist works,

simulations, and so on which are conditioned to increase knowledge and insight, change student attitudes, or to increase skills.

Tools that can help the learning process of students are called learning media. Understanding the implications of media for this process must first gain experience in student learning. Edgar Dale described it in a cone later called the *cone of experience*. This cone of experience is now widely embraced to determine what tools or media are appropriate for students to have an easy learning experience.

The cone of the experience presented (Azis, 2014) Provide an overview that the learning experience obtained by students can be through the process of action or experiencing for themselves what is learned, the process of observing and listening through certain media and the process of listening through language.

The more concretely students study the teaching material, the higher the level of understanding. An example is through direct experience, the more experience obtained by students and vice versa the more abstract students gain experience, for example by using verbal language, the less it will be for students to gain experience.

Through this research, audiovisual media for BIPA students is arranged in part to make it easier for BIPA teachers to teach Indonesian language and culture to foreign speakers optimally and in accordance with real conditions in the field. According to (Azis, 2014), teaching materials have several functions, namely educational functions, social functions, economic functions, political functions, and cultural arts functions. The author believes that foreign speakers will be more interested in exploring BIPA material if all these functions are contained in a quality teaching material.

The implementation of functions that support the value of local wisdom of the Indonesian nation can be realized if the BIPA material includes various elements of local wisdom such as cultural objects, limb movements, physical distance when communicating, worship, customs that apply in the community, value systems that apply in the community, religious systems adopted by the community, livelihoods, art, time utilization, how to stand/sit/respect others, hospitality/reprimand/small talk, praise, mutual assistance, courtesy (Brata Ida Bagus, 2016).

The author in the study developed a multimedia-based material contained in the form of audiovisual adapted from Bretz's Taxonomy which combines local culture and audiovisual. This teaching media uses material in the form of audiovisual illustrations containing language materials of local cultures and Indonesian that can attract foreign speakers and train listening and speaking skills

5. COUCLUSION

In general, in a teaching, especially teaching for BIPA students, a teacher must be skilled and creative in delivering learning. Considering that BIPA students in addition to learning Indonesian language, literature, and culture are required to know the meaning of a speech Indonesian. Audio-visual as teaching material for BIPA students contains audio gestures containing accents typical of Indonesian culture, and national anthems and regional songs that can be applied in BIPA learning.

In general, this study can be concluded that learning materials Indonesian for Foreign Speakers (BIPA), teachers should provide clear and thorough learning goals and should develop learning materials that can accommodate students and attract learners with different learning styles.

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